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AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON BARRIERS AND OPPORTUNITIES IN FOOD-BORNE DISEASE SURVEILLANCE FROM A ONE HEALTH APPROACH WITHIN FOUR EU COUNTRIES

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The title of the study is an adapted version of the title of the task as will be used in the manuscript.

1. The study

The objective of this task was to identify barriers and opportunities for an integrated One Health surveillance of food-borne diseases in selected EU countries. The task was split into two qualitative research studies: one targeting responsible experts and officials (coordination/administration level) of surveillance activities across the food chain in four different countries, and one targeting veterinary practitioners (field level) in one country. The results from these studies can be used to support revision of existing systems, or development of new systems for food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health (OH) perspective.

Coordination level study

The overall aim of this task and study was to identify barriers that hamper the well-functioning of the surveillance systems of food-borne zoonoses, and also to identify opportunities (suggestions) for improvement of these surveillance systems. The objective of this exploratory study was formulated as to investigate experiences and perceptions among persons working at different positions in the field of food-borne zoonoses surveillance within and between countries, and capture examples of factors hampering (barriers) the well-functioning of surveillance systems and examples of suggestions (opportunities) for development or improvement of such systems. The information was collected through interviews. The study focused on any microbiological pathogens causing a food-borne zoonotic disease (e.g. *Salmonella* spp, *Campylobacter* spp).

The results can be used when revising existing systems, or when developing new systems for food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health (OH) perspective. In long term – improved disease surveillance systems can contribute to earlier detection and control of ongoing events and thus minimizing the consequences of such events. The information will be forwarded to participating countries and will be included in a manuscript to be submitted in a peer review journal in the coming months. The study is part of the One-Health European Joint Project [OH-EJP] NOVA project, which aims to develop new surveillance tools and methods and to harmonise and optimise the use of existing surveillance system data.

For the purpose of this study, “barrier” was defined as something such as a rule, law, policy or any other type of obstacle (e.g. technical, ethical, financial, socio-political, educational, constraints in data communication or sharing) that makes it difficult or impossible to achieve a well-functioning food-borne disease surveillance. “Opportunity” represented a suggestion for development or improvement of a system of food-borne disease surveillance.

The main purpose of this study was not to identify or describe in detail all possible barriers and opportunities (i.e. not to give exhaustive detailed description of all of them). However, including some examples covering different types of them can be very useful to improve food-borne disease surveillance from a OH perspective (in other words an inventory of barriers and opportunities, with a few illustrations). Moreover, the study focused on documenting for the first time existing barriers and opportunities in surveillance from professionals with selected profile (see later) who work on food-borne disease surveillance, in order to learn from their experience and suggest improvements. Furthermore, the study does not provide a comparison between countries or systems (countries doing “better” or “worse” in terms of surveillance), but tried to identify similarities and differences in terms of barriers and opportunities and reasons for these. The persons interviewed in the study were a sample of persons working in different domains, at different levels (focus is central, but regional is also possible, depending on the country), in different countries and surveillance systems.

A methodology has been developed and has been put in practice to identify barriers and opportunities in food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health perspective. This information has been collected through interviews with professionals with selected profiles from four countries (Belgium, France, Sweden, Norway) and after development of a number of tools, skills and employment of methodologies:

1. map of food chain (used as a visual tool for cueing) (**see Annex 1**), 2. interview guide document (**see Annex 2**), 3. demographic questionnaire, 4. excel files for collection of data, 5. training on performing interviews and qualitative research, 6. interview try-outs.

The profiles of the professionals interviewed in each of the four countries are the following:

- i. A human epidemiologist (e.g. the head of such a unit or an experienced professional with knowledge of different diseases and managing them)
- ii. A person from administration in charge of planning the annual programmed food chain surveillance (expected to be place at the Min. for Agriculture)
- iii. A veterinary epidemiologist (same as for human epidemiologist)
- iv. A transversal coordinator of a national agency, positioned on the link between risk analysis and risk management
- v. Person from laboratories, ideally the coordinators of the human and veterinary National Reference laboratories (RNL).

The 20 interviews have been performed by three WP1 participants who have received the same training on performing interviews. The information collected by the interviewers has been double-checked and validated from the interviewees to ensure credibility. The information collected through the interviews performed in previous months has been analysed in a standardized qualitative way. The detailed information is provided in the respective deliverable report, while a manuscript is being drafted.

According to the analysis, which was performed following the thematic analysis methodology, the barriers and opportunities identified by the interviewees were grouped in the eight following themes:

1. Data governance, 2. Set-up and operations of the surveillance system, 3. Coordination, 4. Communication, 5. Regulations (political legislations and procedures), 6. Industry's challenges, 7. Funding, 8. Training and education

The most important barriers for all countries were indicated for the themes "Data governance" and "Set-up and operations of the surveillance system". The ideas of barriers and opportunities around these themes are presented in **Annex 3**.

Therefore, the results show that there is room for improvement in food-borne disease surveillance of microbiological pathogens towards a One-Health approach, especially regarding the themes identified as most important (i.e. data governance and the set up and operations of surveillance systems). An analysis of the collected information has also performed per identified theme, taking into account the particularities of each country and will be presented in the content of a manuscript to be submitted in a peer-reviewed journal in the coming months.

The results can be used when revising existing systems, or when developing new systems for food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health (OH) perspective.

Field level study

Early detection of zoonotic and emerging infections is critical for successful handling of outbreaks and control of foodborne diseases. Veterinary practitioners have a key role in the detection of such diseases in livestock. Our objective was to explore how the clinical surveillance and reporting zoonotic and regulated diseases in livestock are perceived and performed by veterinarians in [Sweden](#).

In this study, we conducted in-depth face-to-face interviews with 13 field veterinarians selected based on socio-demographic characteristics. The veterinarians were working in large animal practice. A semi-structured interview guide with open-ended questions and prompts was used to collect qualitative data. The interviews started with general questions to capture the veterinarians' profiles. Thereafter, interviewees were asked to describe their actions in cases of suspected emerging and zoonotic infections under regulation. The discussions followed topics that included their awareness of major disease threats, their perceived role in diseases surveillance, and views on its feasibility. The interviews were transcribed in verbatim followed by thematic analysis of the transcripts using a phenomenological approach.

Themes that commonly appeared were veterinarians, for various reasons, disregarding clinical signs possibly associated with the emerging and zoonotic infections; difficulties to take samples under field

circumstances and to send these samples for diagnostic tests; and aspects related to a communication network involving those taking part of the surveillance system.

These results can serve as a baseline for the design of questionnaire-based surveys, also targeting veterinarians in other countries, as a complementary quantitative approach to investigate clinical surveillance. The results provide suggestions for improvements in the reporting chain. The final goal is to increase the likelihood that a veterinary practitioner promptly contacts animal health authorities when they encounter animals showing signs indicative of diseases under national or EU legislation.

2. Annex I: Adapted map of food chain

At the beginning of the interview, this map (Figure 1) was being shared with each interviewee in order to initiate the discussion and show the framework and range of topics the interview covers (cueing). It also helped by letting the interviewee inform in detail the interviewer the area(s) shown on the map that his/her professional experience covers.

Figure 1. Map of the food chain, adapted for the purposes of this study (i.e. included only aspects of interest to our study). Different locations involved are shown in rectangular schemes, while live organisms/material in elliptical ones.

3. Annex II: Interview guide

The interview guide is a document that was developed in the framework of this study in order to perform the interviews. It includes suggestions for questions and tips for the beginning of the interview and also for after it. The writing style is such as it addresses each interviewer.

The guideline is structured in three sections “warm up-questions”, the “real” questions and a “final” one where the interviewee is given the opportunity to raise anything that might not have been brought up.

3.1 Background (as shared with interviewers)

The topic of this interview is the identification of barriers and opportunities in the surveillance of food-borne zoonoses primarily within each country. In other words, the focus is on food-borne diseases with a OH approach in mind. It is not limited to diseases concerning/involving specific livestock species or to specific pathogens/diseases.

By “barrier” is meant any other type of obstacle that causes problems in disease surveillance. “Opportunity” is any suggestion for development or improvement of food-borne disease surveillance. The interest lies on capturing any type of possible barriers (e.g. from practical issues to behavioural factors) and same goes for the opportunities.

3.2 Guide (as shared with interviewers)

3.2.1. At the beginning of the interview

The interviewer should mention that, as explained in the previous communication with each interviewee via emails, the interview will be recorded. The interviewer should start talking by saying that the process will be open, the interviewees can control what is reported, they can check the interviewers' notes afterwards and the info cannot be traced back to them personally.

Other expressions that can be used if necessary: I want to hear from you.. If at any point you are not willing to answer, let me know..

3.2.2. The questions

“WARM-UP” QUESTIONS

Scenario 1: If the interviewer received the questionnaire (with demographic info) filled in by the interviewee the day before the interview:

The interviewer should ask the interviewee to look at the map already shared (Annex I) and can start by saying something like: “This is a general map of the food chain system (you can name some components). Given the information you shared with us, which parts of on this map of the food chain system does your work/knowledge cover ?”

Scenario 2: If the interviewer has not received the questionnaire (with demographic info) filled in by the interviewee the day before the interview:

The interviewer should first start by filling it in together with the interviewee and continue with the steps as for scenario 1, using appropriate words (e.g. “given what you just told me..”)

“REAL” QUESTIONS

1. From the position where you are and for the food-borne zoonotic topics you work with, what different types of barriers do you identify in food-borne disease surveillance? Can you briefly describe them and explain how surveillance is impaired or hindered by them?
2. Among these, which would you describe as the most important barriers in the surveillance of food-borne zoonoses?
3. Based on your experience, can you give an example (of such barrier(s) in the surveillance of food-borne zoonoses), in a practical context if possible?
4. Do you recall a specific situation when you have faced this barrier? Can you tell a bit about this situation? How did you react to it? Did you/could you take any actions?
(this question is optional, depending on how question 3 will be answered. Question 3 is also about examples that they personally have not faced)
5. In relation to these barriers you described, do you see any opportunities (suggestions) to overcome them/to solve them?
(here keep in mind that this is also about a OH perspective and try to capture it and try to get answers per barrier)
6. Do you have any other more general suggestions and ideas of how the existing food-borne disease surveillance could be improved? How?
(here keep in mind the way they answer in Q5)

FINAL QUESTION

7. We have touched upon many topics, is there any more information that you want to add before we finish the interview?

3.2.3. At the end of interview

Before closing the exchange, the interviewer should remind to the interviewee what will happen after the interview: 1/ for agreement on the notes taken by interviewer and 2/ that it will be always possible to add more comments if needed on the subject, like a barrier or opportunity not suggested during the interview. Ask when they could send this info back (eg suggest a week).

4. Annex III: Presentation of selected results

The most important barriers for all countries were indicated for the themes “Data governance” and “Set-up and operations of the surveillance system”. The ideas of barriers and opportunities around these themes which were mentioned for the different countries are presented in the following figures 2-5.

Figure 2. Barriers in food-borne disease surveillance from a One-Health approach identified around the theme “Data governance” in Belgium, Sweden, France and Norway (in grey and yellow). In yellow are highlighted the barriers identified as more important. The country for which each barrier linked to “Data governance” is mentioned is shown in abbreviation in parenthesis.

Notes: BE: Belgium, S: Sweden, FR: France, NO: Norway, NRL: National Reference Lab, NGS: next generation sequencing.

Figure 3. Opportunities (suggestions) for food-borne disease surveillance from a One-Health approach identified around the theme “Setup and operations of food-borne surveillance” in Belgium, Sweden, France and Norway (in light green and orange). In orange are highlighted the opportunities identified as more important. The country for which each opportunity linked to “Data governance” is mentioned is shown in abbreviation in parenthesis.

Notes: BE: Belgium, S: Sweden, FR: France, NO: Norway, NRL: National Reference Lab, NGS: next generation sequencing, WGS: whole genome sequencing, EU: European Union, f-b: food-borne, VTEC: Verocytotoxin-producing *Escherichia coli*.

Figure 4. Barriers in food-borne disease surveillance from a One-Health approach identified around the theme “Setup and operations of food-borne surveillance” in Belgium, Sweden, France and Norway (in grey and yellow). In yellow are highlighted the barriers identified as more important. The country for which each barrier linked to “Setup and operations” is mentioned in abbreviation in parenthesis.

Notes: BE: Belgium, S: Sweden, FR: France, NO: Norway, f-b: food-borne, VTEC: Verocytotoxin-producing Escherichia coli.

Figure 5. Opportunities (suggestions) for food-borne disease surveillance from a One-Health approach identified around the theme “Setup and operations of food-borne surveillance” in Belgium, Sweden, France and Norway (in light green and orange). In orange is highlighted the opportunity identified as more important. The country for which each opportunity linked to “Setup and operations” is mentioned is shown in abbreviation in parenthesis.

Notes: S: Sweden, FR: France, NO: Norway, f-b: food-borne.